

Zeolite-Encaged Single-Atom Rh Catalysts: Highly-Efficient Hydrogen Generation and Shape-Selective Tandem Hydrogenation of Nitroarenes

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Abstract: Single-atom catalysts are emerging as a new frontier in heterogeneous catalysis for their maximum atom utilization efficiency, but usually suffer from inferior stability. Here, we successfully synthesized single-atom Rh catalysts embedded in MFI-type zeolites under hydrothermal conditions followed by ligand-protected direct H₂ reduction. C_s-corrected scanning transmission electron microscopy and extended X-ray absorption analyses revealed that single Rh atoms were encapsulated within 5-membered rings and stabilized by skeletal oxygens. The resultant catalysts exhibited excellent H₂ generation rates from ammonia borane (AB) hydrolysis, up to 699 min⁻¹ at 298 K, representing the top level among reported heterogeneous catalysts for AB decomposition. Significantly, the catalysts also showed superior catalytic performance in shape-selective tandem hydrogenation of various nitroarenes by coupling with AB dehydrogenation, giving > 99% yield of corresponding amine products. This work demonstrates that the zeolites are ideal supports for encapsulating single metal atoms and can afford high-efficiency shape-selective tandem catalysis.

Introduction

Single-atom catalysts (SACs) with isolated metal atoms dispersed on solid supports, have been emerging as the most active new frontier in heterogeneous catalysis because of the maximum atom-utilization efficiency and unique catalytic properties.^[1] However, SACs usually suffer from inferior stability and poor recyclability in the catalytic processes. The isolated metal atoms are prone to aggregate during synthetic and catalytic procedures due to their higher surface energy than corresponding

metal clusters and nanoparticles; this significantly decreases their catalytic performance and limit the practical applications. The fabrication of SACs with excellent activity and stability is of great significance from both academic and industrial point of views. Zeolites are ideal supports to stabilize metal species for their well-defined microporous channels and excellent thermal stability.^[2] Most importantly, as compared with other solid supports, the zeolite-encaged metal catalysts can be also endowed with unique and excellent shape-selective catalytic performance, which is extremely attractive in the field of catalysis.^[2d, 3] Several subnanometric metal clusters, such as Pd and Pt, had been encapsulated within the silica zeolite matrix via ligand-stabilized or precursor-stabilized methods, which exhibited superior catalytic activity in dehydrogenation and hydrogenation reactions.^[2e, 2g, 2n] Very recently, Liu et al. reported a ligand-protected strategy for preparing isolated metal atoms inside low-silica Y zeolite via thermal calcination-reduction processes.^[2i] However, there is less success in synthesizing zeolite-encaged SACs and there remains a lack of facile and generally applicable synthetic methods to fabricate such catalysts. Moreover, the determination of precise locations of single metal atoms within the zeolite matrix remains a nontrivial task but great challenging.

Hydrogen (H₂) has been regarded as the most environmentally benign energy resource for its high energy density and carbon-free emissions.^[4] Developing efficient and safe methods for H₂ production and storage is of great significance for the future hydrogen economy.^[5] Ammonia-borane (NH₃BH₃, AB) is considered as one of the most outstanding candidates for the chemical H₂ storage and production because of its high hydrogen content, non-toxicity, and superior stability in aqueous solutions.^[5a, 6] So far, many supported metallic catalysts over various substrates, such as carbon materials,^[7] metal oxides,^[8] mesoporous silica^[9] and porous metal-organic frameworks/cages,^[6a, 6b, 10] have been employed for the H₂ generation from AB hydrolysis reactions; but these catalysts are usually subjected to poor long-term and cycling stability. On the other hand, the production of aromatic amines via the hydrogenation of nitroarenes is a popular and important industrial process, because the target amine products are widely used as raw materials or/and intermediates for manufacturing diverse value-added fine chemicals.^[2d, 11] Recently, a tandem route that couples the AB dehydrogenation with hydrogenation of nitro compounds is regarded as an efficient strategy to significantly boost the productivity of the reduction process.^[11] However, the stability and efficiency of catalysts remain key problems to be tackled for achieving high catalytic performance. Until now, there is no report on the zeolite-encaged metal catalysts applied for the tandem reduction of nitro compounds coupled with the highly-

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efficient dehydrogenation of AB hydrolysis while keeping attractive shape-selective activities.

Herein, we developed a facile synthetic method to encapsulate single rhodium (Rh) atoms within **MFI**-type silicalite-1 (S-1) and aluminosilicate ZSM-5 zeolites by using $[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3$ complex as a precursor under one-pot hydrothermal synthesis conditions followed by ligand-protected direct hydrogen reduction. The single-atom nature of Rh was confirmed by detailed C_s -corrected scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), in situ CO-diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFT), and extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) analyses. Significantly, we for the first time revealed the location of the single Rh atoms within sinusoidal 5-membered rings (MRs) of **MFI** and stabilized by skeletal oxygens. The resultant catalysts exhibited excellent H_2 generation rate from AB hydrolysis. Most significantly, the zeolite-encaged single-atom Rh catalysts showed superior shape-selective catalytic performance in tandem hydrogenation of diverse nitroarenes by coupling with AB dehydrogenation, giving > 99% yield of corresponding amine products, which is three orders of magnitude higher than that using the H_2 as a reduction agent. This work demonstrates the great advantages of zeolites in encaging single metal atoms, improving catalytic performance, affording catalytic shape selectivity, and promising tandem catalytic reactions.

Results and Discussion

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the fabrication of Rh@S-1 catalyst.

As shown in Scheme 1, the Rh atoms confined within S-1 zeolites were prepared by the in-situ hydrothermal synthesis in the reaction gel with molar composition of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{TPAOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3 = 1/0.4/35/2.25 \times 10^{-3}$ followed by ligand-protected direct reduction in pure H_2 at 500°C . The obtained samples were named as Rh@S-1-H. For comparison, the Rh@S-1-C sample prepared via a conventional calcination (550°C in the air)-reduction (400°C in H_2) procedure and the Rh/S-1-im sample prepared by incipient wetness impregnation method were also synthesized. Thermogravimetric-differential thermal (TG-DTA), solid ^{13}C MAS NMR, and elemental CHN analysis indicated that the $[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3$ complexes remained intact during the synthesis process and were encapsulated inside zeolites (Figures S1, S2 and Table S1). Powder X-ray diffraction measurements revealed that all Rh-

containing samples possessed the **MFI** topological structure, implying that the encapsulated metal species do not affect the crystallization of zeolites (Figure S3). The Rh loading amount in all of the samples was measured as 0.28 wt% by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES).

C_s -corrected high-angle annular dark-field STEM (HAADF-STEM) and high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images of samples are shown in Figures 1 and S4. Initially, it can be observed that in any type of as-synthesized samples excellent crystallinity is retained and the 10-membered ring (MR) channels of **MFI** are empty along the b-axis of the nanosized S-1 zeolites (~ 200 nm) (Figure 1A). As in this mode, the contrast is sensitive to the atomic number of the elements, and brighter signals can be directly inferred to the presence of Rh within the zeolite cages. For Rh@S-1-H, a small number of signals can be observed in some regions of the zeolite framework due to the presence of atomically dispersed Rh atoms (Figures 1A and B). However, for the Rh@S-1-C, very clear homogeneously-distributed Rh clusters can be observed (Figures 1C and D).

Figure 1. C_s -corrected STEM images of A, B) Rh@S-1-H and C, D) Rh@S-1-C viewed along b-axis orientation, E-G) Rh@S-1-H viewed along [011] orientation as well as the schematic models on the same projection. H) HAADF-STEM image of Rh@S-1-H and the corresponding EDX mapping images for O, Si, and Rh elements.

Considering the three-dimensional nature of the zeolite crystals, different crystallographic orientations were taken in order to achieve a clear location of the Rh species. Along the [010] orientation all forming units are observable: these are 10-MRs, 6-MRs, and 5-MRs (see Figure 1A). However, on the [011] orientation the projection is very dense, and it does not allow to discern between atomic columns or even membered rings; and only “rectangular units” (see Figures 1E-G) can be discerned, marked by a red circle. Notably, these units are only formed by the sinusoidal 5 MRs; the contrast observed there can be only owed to the presence of Rh species confined within these rings (Figures 1E-G). In the models presented in Figure 1G, a

rectangular unit is marked in yellow that would correspond to the 5 MRs along the [011] and [010], respectively. All above C_s -corrected STEM analyses confirm that single Rh atoms are formed and encapsulated within sinusoidal 5 MRs of zeolite crystals in Rh@S-1-H samples. Moreover, all Rh atoms in both Rh@S-1-H and Rh@S-1-C samples are totally encapsulated within zeolites and no Rh species are observable on the outer surface of zeolite crystals. Elemental mappings analysis for the Rh@S-1-H further suggests that the Rh atoms are homogeneously dispersed throughout zeolite crystals (Figure 1I). In contrast, the Rh/S-1-im displays different situations that many large and uneven Rh nanoparticles (NPs) (> 5 nm) are located outside of zeolites (Figure S4). Back-scattering scanning electron microscopy (SEM) shows that no Rh species can be detected on the outer surface of Rh@S-1-H and Rh@S-1-C, but some larger Rh NPs can be observed outside of Rh/S-1-im (Figure S5).

These data indicate that the in-situ hydrothermal synthesis method followed by ligand-protected direct H_2 reduction treatment possesses significant advantages for the fabrication of small-sized metal species confined within zeolite matrix than the incipient wetness impregnation method. Significantly, compared with the conventional calcination-reduction treatment, the ligand-protected direct H_2 reduction method can further decrease the sizes of metal species with an atomic-scale dispersion, in which the organic ligands and templates can serve as protective agents to inhibit the aggregation of metal species during the reduction process. TG-DTA analysis revealed that no exothermic peaks can be observed in both Rh@S-1-H and Rh@S-1-C, indicating all organic species were completely removed under the calcination and/or reduction processes (Figure S6); this was further confirmed by elemental CHN analyses (Table S1). The encapsulated metal species in zeolite caused a slight decrease of microporous volume (~ 0.012 cm^3/g), but large microporous volumes (0.094 and 0.099 cm^3/g) and areas (234 and 245 m^2/g) retained in Rh@S-1-H and Rh@S-1-C, respectively (Figure S7).

zeolite-encaged Rh catalysts at Rh K-edge. The peak intensity of the Rh foil is multiplied by a coefficient. D) In-situ CO-DRIFT spectra of the samples.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis shows that the peaks at 307.5 and 312.2 eV ascribed to Rh $3d_{7/2}$ and Rh $3d_{5/2}$ of Rh (0) are observable in Rh/S-1-im sample, but no XPS signals are detectable in Rh@S-1-H and Rh@S-1-C, further indicating that all Rh atoms are completely encaged inside zeolites (Figure 2A).^[12] The Rh@S-1-H samples with higher Rh/Si ratios of $3.4 \sim 6.75 \times 10^{-3}$ in the initial synthesis gels, giving Rh loadings in zeolites of 0.45 \sim 0.71 wt% (determined by ICP-AES, Table S2), were also prepared via ligand-protected direct H_2 reduction method (Figure S8). Uniformly-dispersed Rh atoms without clear Rh clusters are observed in HRTEM images even if the Rh loading is increased to 0.71 wt% (Figure S9).

The X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) and extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) spectra of the samples were measured to determine the electronic and structural information of Rh species. The detailed structural parameters based on EXAFS fittings are summarized in Table S3. The Rh K-edge XANES spectra in Figure 2B indicates that all zeolite-encaged Rh species possess a higher oxidation state than the Rh foil due to the formation of ultrafine Rh species.^[10] Compared to Rh@S-1-C, the increased intensity of the white line and a small shift to the higher binding energy are observed for Rh@S-1-H, suggesting their higher oxidation state. Based on the EXAFS fitting results (Figure 2C), the average coordination number (CN) of the Rh-O shell (the bond distance of ca. 2.04 Å) for Rh@S-1-H is 4.6 ± 0.1 , which is higher than that of Rh@S-1-C (3.3 ± 0.3). No Rh-Rh peak and Rh-O-Rh peak attributed to the second shell of rhodium oxide can be detected in Rh@S-1-H, demonstrating that isolated Rh atoms are formed and stabilized by the oxygen atoms in the zeolite frameworks. In contrast, the peak at 2.70 Å corresponding to Rh-Rh metallic bond (CN = 1.4 ± 0.2) is observable in Rh@S-1-C. It indicates that some subnanometric Rh clusters are formed in the Rh@S-1-C, which is in accordance with the observation of C_s -correct STEM measurements. Notably, there is still no Rh-Rh and Rh-O-Rh peaks can be observed in Rh@S-1-H even if the Rh loading reaches up to 0.71 wt%, suggesting the Rh species remains atomically distributed at a high Rh content. In-situ CO-DRIFT measurements were further employed to characterize the structure of Rh species. As shown in Figure 2D, two peaks at 2092 and 2023 cm^{-1} attributed to the symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching of CO from the isolated mononuclear $Rh^I(CO)_2$ species are observed in Rh@S-1-H;^[2h] however, only the peak at 2048 cm^{-1} attributed to the linear-adsorbed CO on Rh NPs is observable in Rh/S-1-im, but this peak barely exists in Rh@S-1-H, further demonstrating that the Rh species in Rh@S-1-H are atomically dispersed. Significantly, the Rh@S-1-H exhibited excellent high-temperature stability under various atmospheres. No clear Rh clusters were observed even after calcination in H_2 at 700 °C and the Rh sizes were only increased to 1.5 and 1.0 nm after calcination in O_2 at 700 °C and water-vapor

Figure 2. A) XPS spectra of various samples. B) Rh K-edge XANES spectra and C) Fourier transform of k^2 -weighted EXAFS spectra of Rh foil and various

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treatment at 600 °C, respectively (Figures S10-13). Moreover, after calcination treatments in various atmospheres, no metal species can be observed on the outside of zeolite crystals. In contrast, the particle size of Rh NPs in Rh/S-1-im dramatically increased to 5.9 and 11.5 nm and located on the outer surface of zeolite crystals after calcination in H₂ and O₂ 700 °C, respectively (Figure S14). Significantly, the structure of zeolites and Rh contents of Rh@S-1-H kept unchanged after thermal/hydrothermal treatments (Figure S15 and Table S2).

Figure 3. A-D) C_s-corrected STEM images of Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105) with different magnifications and orientations. Atomic resolution image of a typical crystal on the [010] showing the Fourier Diffraction pattern and a closer look with the model superimposed are inset into Figure B.

The direct H₂-reduction strategy can be also extended to encapsulate single Rh atoms into aluminosilicate ZSM-5 zeolite with various Si/Al ratios (Figure S16). TEM measurements reveal that the introduction of Al atoms into the zeolite frameworks leads to an irregular crystal morphology and the Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105) shows an aggregated morphology consisting of many small nanocrystals (Figures S17-18). All Rh species are encapsulated within ZSM-5 crystals, and no Rh clusters are clearly observable both inside and outside of crystals. ICP-AES measurements reveal that the Rh loading amounts of Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 245) and Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105) are 0.30 and 0.32 wt%, respectively. To get the clear location of Rh species inside ZSM-5 crystals, the C_s-corrected STEM images were recorded on the Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105). As shown in Figure 3, the introduction of metal species does not break the zeolite structure and excellent crystallinity is retained. 10 MR channels are empty as observed along the b-axis of the crystals. Notably, single Rh atoms are clearly observed inside the zeolites (inside the red circles in Figure 3C) and located within the sinusoidal 5-MRs (Figure 3D), which is the same as the case of Rh@S-1-H.

Figure 4. A) Volume of generated H₂ versus reaction time for the dehydrogenation of AB (1 M, 1 mL) catalyzed by various catalysts at 298 K ($n_{Rh}/n_{AB} = 0.0011$); B) Volume of generated H₂ versus reaction time for the dehydrogenation of AB (1 M, 1 mL) catalyzed by Rh@S-1-H at different temperatures ($n_{Rh}/n_{AB} = 0.0011$), insert of B) Arrhenius plot (\ln TOF versus $1000/T$). C) Recycling stability tests over Rh@S-1-H. D) Volume of generated H₂ versus reaction time for the dehydrogenation of AB in the mixed solution of water/methanol with or without nitroarenes catalyzed by Rh@S-1-H at 298 K ($n_{Rh}/n_{AB} = 0.0011$, volume of water/methanol = 10 mL/8 mL, $n_{AB} = 1$ mmol, $n_{nitroarene} = 0.1$ mmol).

Figure 4A shows the catalytic performance for H₂ generation from the AB dehydrogenation at 298 K catalyzed by various catalysts. The Rh@S-1-H catalyst completed the decomposition of AB (1 mmol) with an H₂/AB ratio of 3 within 6.33 min, affording a high TOF value of 432 mol_{H₂} mol_{Rh}⁻¹ min⁻¹, being more than 2- and 6-fold higher than that of Rh@S-1-C (195 mol_{H₂} mol_{Rh}⁻¹ min⁻¹) and Rh/S-1-im (65 mol_{H₂} mol_{Rh}⁻¹ min⁻¹), respectively. The improved catalytic activity can be attributed to the reduced size of Rh species that can expose more active sites for the AB decomposition. Notably, the H₂ generation rate can be further accelerated over Rh@ZSM-5-H catalysts. It is attributed to the synergistic effect between Rh species and Brønsted acidic sites of ZSM-5 zeolite, which can activate both AB and water molecules, respectively, and enhance the H₂ production efficiency in accordance with our previous work.^[13] The dehydrogenation rates were further improved in line with the increased acid concentration of zeolites (Figure S19). The TOF value of Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105) increased to 699 min⁻¹ at 298 K, representing the top level among all of the state-of-the-art heterogeneous catalysts for the AB decomposition.^[6a, 7a, 8b, 10a, 14] All products were determined by gas chromatography analysis and ¹H NMR and ¹¹B NMR measurements (Figures S20-22). The decomposition of AB follows the equation as follow:

The H₂ generation rates can be improved with the increase of reaction temperatures. The TOF value over Rh@S-1-H reached up to 1829 min⁻¹ at 313 K and the apparent activation energy of

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Rh@S-1-H was calculated as 75.5 kJ mol^{-1} (Figure 4B and S23). Kinetic studies of AB hydrolysis over Rh@S-1-H were also investigated. As shown in Figures S24 and S25, the H_2 generation rates were gradually improved with the increase of the catalyst concentrations, but they were hardly dependent on the AB concentrations. The logarithmic plots of reaction rates versus catalyst concentrations gave a slope of 1.22 (Figure S26), suggesting the first-order kinetics with respect to the catalyst concentration. Significantly, the Rh@S-1-H possessed excellent recycling stability during the AB dehydrogenation, the H_2 generation rate, the crystallinity of zeolites and size of Rh species remained unchanged after five consecutive cycles (Figures 4C, S27-S29).

The catalytic activity of Rh@S-1-H and Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105) catalysts for the tandem reactions that coupled the AB dehydrogenation with nitroarene hydrogenation at 298 K were also investigated. The results are shown in Table 1 and Figures S30-S46. The nitrobenzene can be completely converted to aniline with > 99% selectivity of aniline within 1.5 and 1 min over Rh@S-1-H and Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105), affording a high TOF value to 60.6 and $90.9 \text{ mol}_{\text{nitrobenzene}} \text{ mol}_{\text{Rh}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively, being 2 and 3-fold higher than that of commercial Rh/C catalysts. In contrast, the conversion of nitrobenzene was as low as 3% after 15 h, when the AB was replaced by 1 bar of H_2 . Moreover, no product can be detected without adding catalysts. Above all results indicate that the tandem hydrogenation reaction is much efficient than the conventional reduction process by using H_2 as a hydrogen source; this is because the H_2 can be in-situ generated inside zeolite upon dehydrogenation of AB which can further reduce the nitroarenes. The efficiency of tandem nitrobenzene hydrogenation can be improved in line with the increase of hydrogen generation rate from the AB dehydrogenation. Moreover, after five consecutive runs of nitrobenzene hydrogenation over Rh@S-1-H, the catalytic activity kept unchanged, indicating their excellent durability during the tandem reaction. Most significantly, the Rh@S-1-H and Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105) also exhibited superior shape-selective catalytic activity for the hydrogenation of various nitroarenes with different molecule sizes. The p-fluoronitrobenzene, p-chloronitrobenzene, p-bromonitrobenzene, p-nitroaniline, p-dinitrobenzene, and p-nitrotoluene (entries 2-7) can be completely converted into the corresponding amines with excellent selectivity (> 99%) within 2–10 min over Rh@S-1-H. In contrast, no conversion can be observable when the 3-nitrotoluene and 4-nitroxylylene were used as substrates over Rh@S-1-H and Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105) even after 60 min (entries 8 and 9), while the 4-nitroxylylene gave a complete conversion over Rh/S-1-im within 5 min. Above results show that an excellent shape-selective system can be efficiently established by using Rh@zeolite as a catalyst, but failed to succeed over the Rh/S-1-im catalyst. To better understand the process of the tandem reaction, the AB hydrolysis over Rh@S-1-H under the nitroarene hydrogenation condition were also investigated. 73.5 mL of H_2 (AB/ H_2 = 3) was generated within 14 min without nitroarenes; however, the volume of generated H_2

decreased to 66 mL when the nitrobenzene was introduced into the reaction solution (Figure 4D). It indicated that a part of generated H_2 from AB hydrolysis was consumed by the reduction of nitrobenzene, suggesting the tandem catalytic process of AB hydrolysis and nitroarene hydrogenation. In contrast, the H_2 production was not affected with the introduction of 4-nitroxylylene into the reaction system, further indicating the 4-nitroxylylene could not contact with the Rh species within S-1 zeolites for the tandem reaction.

Table 1. Tandem reactions of the AB dehydrogenation and hydrogenation of nitroarenes over different Rh-based catalysts.

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time /min	Con./Sel %/%
1 ^[a]			1.5	100/>99
1 ^[b]			3	100/>99
1 ^[c]			900	5/>99
1 ^[d]			120	Trace
1 ^[e]			1	100/>99
1 ^[f]			1.5	100/>99
2 ^[a]			5	100/>99
3 ^[a]			5	100/>99
4 ^[a]			5	100/>99
5 ^[a]			2	100/>99
6 ^[a]			2	100/>99
7 ^[a]			10	100/>99
8 ^[a]			60	Trace
8 ^[e]			60	Trace
9 ^[a]			60	Trace
9 ^[e]			60	Trace
9 ^[g]			5	100/>99

[a] Catalyst: Rh@S-1-H; [b] Catalyst: commercial Rh/C; Reaction condition of a and b: 0.1 mmol of nitroarene, 1 mmol of NH_3BH_3 , the ratio of Rh/substrate is 0.011, MeOH/ H_2O = 8mL/10mL, 298 K; [c] Replacing NH_3BH_3 by 1 bar of H_2 ; [d] Without adding any catalyst; [e] Catalyst: Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al = 105); [f] by

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using Rh@S-1-H as a catalyst after 5th cycles. [g] Catalyst: Rh/S-1-im; [h] All products were identified by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry measurements.

Conclusion

In summary, single Rh atoms were successfully encapsulated within MFI zeolites via a facile ligand-protected direct H₂-reduction method. Detailed C_s-corrected STEM, CO-DRIFT, and EXAFS measurements revealed the single-atom nature of the embedded Rh atoms which were located within sinusoidal 5-MRs and stabilized by skeletal oxygens of zeolite. The Rh@S-1-H and Rh@ZSM-5-H (Si/Al =105) catalysts exhibited superior H₂ generation rate from AB hydrolysis, affording TOF values of 432 and 699 mol_{H₂} mol_{Rh}⁻¹ min⁻¹ at 298 K, respectively, representing the top level among all of the state-of-the-art catalysts ever reported. Most significantly, the zeolite-encaged single-atom metallic catalyst exhibited superior efficiency in tandem hydrogenation of nitroarenes by coupling with AB dehydrogenation; meanwhile these catalysts afforded shape selectivity for various nitroarenes and showed excellent recycling stability. This work not only demonstrates the zeolites are an ideal supports for encaging single metal atoms with the excellent stability and catalytic activity, but also open up new perspectives for the application of such catalysts in shape-selective tandem catalytic reactions.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords: heterogeneous catalysis • zeolites • hydrogen generation • single-atom catalyst • tandem reaction

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Table of Contents

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Single Rh atoms were encapsulated within **MFI** zeolites under in-situ hydrothermal conditions followed by ligand-protected direct H₂-reduction. The catalyst gave a high turnover frequency of 699 mol_{H₂} (mol_{Rh})⁻¹ min⁻¹ at 298 K for ammonia borane (AB) hydrolysis and exhibited superior catalytic efficiency in shape-selective tandem hydrogenation of nitroarenes by coupling with AB decomposition.

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Zeolite-Encaged Single-Atom Rh Catalysts: Highly-Efficient Hydrogen Generation and Shape-Selective Tandem Hydrogenation of Nitroarenes